

PROOF OF PROP. 1

We show here how to construct a splitting satisfying Prop. 1. For the majority of cases we will construct a path p such that the splitting is $[(ua), p, (bu)]$ as described in the main document. In a few cases, we will explicitly construct the splitting cycle without using u or p . Recall from the main document that in order for the splitting to result in sphere triangulations with fewer vertices, it must partition \mathcal{T} into regions with at least two interior vertices each.

We define an *isolated vertex* to be a boundary vertex of $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$ with degree 2. Isolated vertices are impossible to build path p from since they have no path to the interior of $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$. For the rest of the proof we will repeatedly reference the labeled cases in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3. These figures depict $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$ with the following color coding. The purple vertex is an arbitrary isolated vertex. The red vertex is labeled a , and the green vertex is labeled b . Cyan vertices are optionally present to indicate that \mathcal{C} has more than or equal to 6 vertices.

Case 0 First, we consider the case where no vertices on \mathcal{C} are isolated. We can choose a and b arbitrarily as long as they are 3 or more edges apart in \mathcal{C} and compute p as the shortest path between them in the interior of $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$. If such a path is found, then we have our splitting. If the path does not exist, there must be an interior edge e between boundary vertices on \mathcal{C} separating a from b . Since no isolated vertices exist, we can simply choose endpoints of e as the new a and b with $p = e$. This is illustrated by the first image of Figure 1.

The rest of the proof considers the case where at least one isolated vertex i_0 exists. Let its neighboring vertices be i_1, i_2 . (i_0, i_1, i_2) must be a triangle in $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$ with an interior edge (i_1, i_2) . Since every interior edge is adjacent to two triangles, flipping across (i_1, i_2) brings us to a triangle we will denote t . t can be arranged in a few different ways.

Case 1a The triangle t is completed with a boundary vertex adjacent to i_2 . Without loss of generality, i_1 is exchangeable with i_2 . This is illustrated in the second image of Figure 1. The single red edge in t is p .

Case 1b The triangle t can be completed with a boundary vertex not adjacent to either i_1 or i_2 . This is illustrated in the third image of Figure 1. As long as one or more cyan vertices are present, the red edge separates \mathcal{C} such that both sides have at least 2 interior vertices.

Case 1c This case is identical to Case 1b except there are no cyan vertices i.e. \mathcal{C} has exactly 6 vertices. This configuration is special in that we are unable to split \mathcal{T} into two triangulations each with fewer than 7 vertices. Thus the full sphere triangulation is depicted including u and its neighborhood \mathcal{U} with dashed edges in the fourth image of Figure 1. For this configuration, we specify the full splitting by the red edges. This splitting turns the sphere triangulation into

$$(3, 0, 3, 1) = (2, 2, 2) +_4 (1, 3, 3).$$

Even though the number of vertices in one of the resulting triangulations is still 7, all vertex degrees are less than or equal to 5, thus they are base cases.

Case 2 The last possibility is that triangle t is completed with one interior vertex i_3 of $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$. We illustrate this in the first image of Figure 2 and refer to its labels. Since i_2 is adjacent to both i_3 and d there must be a path from i_3 to d that is entirely adjacent to i_2 . This is indicated by the dashed black edge. The rest of Case 2 enumerates different possibilities for this path.

Case 2a If the path is fully on the interior of $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$, then p is indicated by the red edges in the second image of Figure 2.

Case 2b If the path connects i_3 to any vertex labeled f in the third image of Figure 2, then p is indicated by the red edges.

Case 2c The only remaining possibility is that the path connects i_3 to g depicted in the fourth image of Figure 2. Assuming at least one cyan vertex is present, the red edges form p .

Case 3 If there are no cyan vertices, i.e. \mathcal{C} contains only 6 vertices, then the red edges from Case 2c do not partition \mathcal{C} into two regions of at least two interior vertices. In this setting we consider the last few cases.

Case 3a If there is an interior path from i_3 to i_4 as labeled in the first image of Figure 3, then the red edges form p .

Case 3b, 3c The only way for the interior path from case 3a to not exist is if an edge prevents an interior path between i_3 and i_4 . This edge is labeled (i_1, i_5) in the second and third images of Figure 3. These two images show explicit splittings for \mathcal{T} in the case that there is an interior vertex of $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$ that is not i_3 .

Figure 1: Illustrations of $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$ in various situations. This figure considers the cases where there are no isolated vertices, or when there is at least one isolated vertex and t has all its vertices on \mathcal{C} .

Figure 2: Illustrations of $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$ in various situations. This figure considers the cases where t has one vertex on the interior of $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$ and \mathcal{C} has more than 6 vertices.

Figure 3: Illustrations of $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$ in various situations. This figure considers the cases where t has one vertex on the interior of $\mathcal{T} - \mathcal{U}$ and \mathcal{C} has exactly 6 vertices.

Case 3d Finally, if there are no interior vertices of $\mathcal{T}-\mathcal{U}$ except for i_3 , then we know the full sphere triangulation \mathcal{T} . This triangulation has signature $(4,0,0,4)$ and is fully depicted in the last image of Figure 3. The red edges indicate the following splitting:

$$(4, 0, 0, 4) = (3, 0, 3, 1) +_5 (1, 3, 3, 1).$$

Both of the resulting sphere triangulations are base cases.

In summary, we have explicitly constructed splittings of \mathcal{T} that result in two sphere triangulations each with fewer vertices than \mathcal{T} . The two exceptions are cases 1c and 3d where we construct splittings that result in base cases.